

因應中共多模態認知滲透作戰的新型對策： 建制大型語料庫數據分析的資安語言學新取徑

摘要

有鑒於臺灣逐年受到中共「認知領域滲透作戰」的大量攻擊，本文針對資安國防概念下位的認知戰層面，提出了臺灣可以採取與建立的新型應對措施機制。本文主要係針對了中共認知滲透作戰作為評估對象，發展資安語言學政策上的方針建議，期許容或可作為未來國防資訊安全的政策建言參照。本文嘗試在較為硬理論的面向上，提供資安語言學文本探勘結合言談解構等質性與量化工具盒整合分析的概括方法論。期許本文的研究結果，往後得以使我方能組成相關跨領域專家團隊，來因應中共認知滲透作戰攻擊之挑戰。

關鍵詞：認知滲透作戰、大數據語料庫、資安語言學、文本探勘分析、敘事
語言解構

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網路新聞專欄與報導

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網際網路平台連結

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Using Linguistics Corpus Data Analysis to Combat PRC's Cognitive Infiltration

Abstract

In light of Taiwan's extensive exposure to the Chinese Communist Party's "cognitive domain infiltration warfare," this paper proposes new response mechanisms and strategies for cybersecurity and national defense. The focus is primarily on assessing the CCP's cognitive infiltration tactics to develop policy recommendations in cybersecurity linguistics. These recommendations are intended to serve as a reference for future national defense and information security policies. Within the constraints of limited resources, this study attempts to provide an integrated analysis method combining qualitative and quantitative tools. This method involves text mining in cybersecurity linguistics, focusing on "textual content" and incorporating discourse deconstruction. The aim is to enhance the success rate in identifying and defining contentious information in cognitive warfare, thereby offering policy suggestions.

Keywords: Cognitive Infiltration, Big Data Corpus, Cybersecurity Linguistics, Text Mining Analysis, Narrative Language Deconstruction.